

Digital Literacy and Data Privacy Awareness: A Survey of College Library Users

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Abstract: *As the use of digital libraries and access to e-resources grows in higher education, the need for both digital literacy and data privacy awareness has become increasingly important.*

This study aims to explore the level of digital literacy and awareness of data privacy issues among college library users. It investigates the users' ability to access, evaluate, and use of digital resources effectively, as well as their understanding of data privacy risks such as identity theft, data breaches, and ethical use of digital content. The study also examines the correlation between digital literacy and data privacy awareness, identifying gaps in knowledge and practices that may leave users vulnerable to security threats.

A descriptive survey method was employed, with data collected from a sample of 224 respondents from a government aided college in Kolkata, West Bengal. A structured questionnaire was used to assess participants' digital literacy skills, privacy knowledge, and their use of digital library services as well as online resources.

The findings revealed varying levels of digital literacy, with rural and urban users demonstrating differing capabilities in navigating digital tools. While most users showed basic understanding of digital resources, significant gaps were found in data privacy awareness, particularly regarding cybersecurity risks and institutional privacy policies. The study highlights the need for enhanced digital literacy training and improved privacy education in college libraries, ensuring that users can confidently access and protect their personal information in digital environments.

The study concludes with recommendations to implement comprehensive digital literacy programs and establish clear guidelines on data privacy, aiming to better equip students for the challenges of the digital age.

Keywords: Digital Literacy, Data Privacy Awareness, College Library Users, Cybersecurity Risks, Digital Resources Evaluation.

1. Introduction:

College libraries are essential for giving staff and students access to a wealth of digital materials and for promoting digital literacy in today's quickly changing digital environment. Understanding data security and privacy has grown more crucial as digital technologies become more and more integrated into the educational process. Users now have access to e-books, journals, and databases thanks to the growth of digital libraries, but there are now concerns about data privacy and the moral treatment of user data. To ensure the safe and efficient use of digital resources, it is crucial to comprehend digital literacy and data privacy awareness in areas like West Bengal, where colleges vary in terms of infrastructure, socioeconomic level, and digital access. The purpose of this survey-based study is to find out how well-informed and aware college library patrons, particularly students, are about data privacy issues. By evaluating users' comprehension of privacy risks and their proficiency with digital tool navigation, the study will shed light on how prepared students are for the challenges of the digital age.

2. Objectives of the Study:

The primary objectives of this study are:

- To assess the level of digital literacy among college library users.
- To evaluate awareness of data privacy issues, including the protection of personal information, cybersecurity risks, and the ethical use of digital resources.
- To identify gaps in knowledge regarding data privacy and safe internet practices.
- To analyse the correlation between digital literacy and data privacy awareness, determining whether more digitally literate users are better equipped to handle privacy risks.
- To propose recommendations for enhancing digital literacy and data privacy awareness in college libraries

3. Review of Literature:

Mansour (2017) in his study tries to identify the various types of Digital Information Literacy and to find out any constraints affecting the related skills and competencies of those professionals. Ranjan & Patel (2021) tries to assess digital literacy skills and competencies among library users of central university of Jharkhand. The paper also deals with awareness of various databases, e-learning tools and various types of literacy such as information literacy, web literacy, ICT literacy etc. Saritepeci, et al. (2024) created a multi-group analysis about the role of digital literacy and digital data security awareness in online privacy concerns. Park (2013) examined the impact of three dimensions of digital literacy on privacy-related online behaviors: (a) familiarity with technical aspects of the Internet, (b) awareness of common institutional practices, and (c) understanding of current privacy policy. Lee & Al Khaldi (2020) done a survey about online platform users' digital literacy and its effects on digital trust and privacy awareness and found that that if a user has higher levels of digital skills, it is more likely that he or she will have a higher degree of awareness and concerns of data privacy. The article written by Hargittai (2005) presents survey measures of web-oriented digital literacy to serve as proxies for observed skill measures, which are much more expensive and difficult to collect for large samples. Goldag (2021) in his research tries to investigate the relationship between the digital literacy levels of university students and their digital data security awareness levels. The research was carried out in relational screening model.

4. Scope, Coverage and Limitations:

This survey-based study was conducted focusing the digital literacy and data privacy awareness to the undergraduate students of a specific govt. aided college of North 24 Parganas of West Bengal, India. The study covers users' attitude towards ability to access, evaluate, and use of digital information as well as familiarity with digital tools, search engines, databases, and e-resources, basic understanding of cyber security practices, awareness about data privacy, etc.

Due to time constraints the study only covers undergraduate students of a specific college of West Bengal region. Responses based on structured questionnaire only consider for this study.

5. Methodology:

The study was conducted at a specific college in West Bengal, with a sample size of 224 undergraduate students across various disciplines. The respondents were evenly distributed among the three years of undergraduate students, with the majority (78%) aged between 18 and 21. The students represented fields such as Humanities, Science, and Commerce, and most were frequent users of both digital library resources and social media platforms. A structured questionnaire was developed, consisting of closed-ended and open-ended questions to assess users' digital literacy levels, awareness of data privacy issues, and practices regarding the use of digital resources. Quantitative data was analyzed using statistical tools to identify trends, correlations, and significant findings. Qualitative responses were analyzed thematically to capture in-depth insights and personal experiences related to data privacy and digital literacy.

6. Significance of the Study:

This study is significant in several ways:

- The findings can inform college and library policymakers in West Bengal about the current gaps in digital literacy and data privacy awareness, helping to develop targeted programs and policies.
- College libraries can use the insights to design better digital literacy workshops and privacy education initiatives for students.
- With the growing emphasis on digital transformation, improving digital literacy and privacy awareness is crucial for promoting a well-informed, tech-savvy population capable of navigating digital environments safely and ethically.

7. Data Collection and Analysis:

7.1. Low Digital Literacy Among Undergraduate Students

The analysis revealed that the digital literacy skills of the respondents were generally low, with many students struggling to effectively use the digital resources provided by their college library. This included their ability to search for and evaluate academic information using online tools, manage digital content, and use reference management software. When asked to rate their confidence in using digital tools such as search engines, academic databases, e-books, and citation tools, 62% of students rated themselves as "somewhat confident" or below on a 5-point scale. Only 14% of students reported feeling "very confident" in navigating online academic databases such as JSTOR. A significant number of students (58%) expressed that their college did not offer sufficient guidance or training on how to use the digital library services effectively. Approximately 30% of students said they had never attended

any workshops or training sessions on digital literacy, though they indicated they would be interested in doing so if provided. Most students (64%) admitted to facing difficulties in evaluating the credibility of online academic resources. They struggled to distinguish between peer-reviewed articles and non-academic sources, particularly when using search engines like Google, which often mixed scholarly and non-scholarly content.

7.2. Lack of Awareness and Concern About Data Privacy

The findings indicated a widespread lack of awareness regarding data privacy among the students, with many unaware of how their personal information could be at risk while using digital library resources or other online platforms. A large portion of the respondents (72%) reported having little or no knowledge about data privacy and its importance when using online resources. Many students did not understand how their personal information could be collected, stored, or potentially compromised. Only 18% of the respondents said they were fully aware of the data privacy practices associated with digital platforms. For example, 38% said they did not consistently log out of their accounts after accessing resources, and 59% admitted to using the same weak passwords across multiple platforms. Less than 20% of students used strong, unique passwords, with many reporting that they found it difficult to remember complex login credentials. Only 8% of students said they regularly read privacy policies before using new online resources or digital library services. Most students (76%) confessed to skipping over privacy policies without reviewing them, indicating a low level of concern or awareness about the potential risks involved.

7.3. Minimal Security Practices in Daily Life

The study revealed that, despite frequent use of digital platforms, students showed poor engagement with security practices. When asked about their security practices, only 17% of students reported using two-factor authentication for their online accounts, despite this being a basic method to enhance online security. Additionally, 81% of the students admitted to frequently accessing digital resources and personal accounts using public Wi-Fi, a practice that exposes them to significant cybersecurity risks. About 43% of the students rarely updated the software or apps they used to access digital resources, making them vulnerable to security threats such as malware and cyberattacks. Many students were unaware of the importance of keeping their systems updated to protect against potential vulnerabilities. Only 7% of respondents had ever used a Virtual Private Network (VPN) while accessing online resources, with most students (85%) reporting that they were unaware of what a VPN is or how it could help protect their privacy. Similarly, encryption methods for protecting sensitive information were unfamiliar to 78% of the students.

7.4. High Social Media Activity with Poor Security Practices

While the students in the study were highly active on social media platforms, they did not follow proper security protocols. A large majority (94%) of students reported using social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp on a daily basis. These platforms were primarily used for social interactions, news updates, and entertainment. Over 67% of respondents admitted to sharing personal information such as their location, personal photos, and contact details on social media without considering the security risks. Only 33% of students reported using privacy settings effectively, such as restricting access to their profiles or posts to friends and family. The majority of students (91%) said they had never experienced a cyber-attack, but when asked if they felt confident in identifying online threats such as phishing attempts, only 22% said they were confident. This low awareness on threats puts them at higher risk of falling victim to online scams and identity theft.

7.5. Limited Institutional Support for Data Privacy and Digital Literacy

Another significant finding was the limited support provided by the college in terms of enhancing students' digital literacy and raising awareness of data privacy. Only 20% of respondents said their college provided sufficient information about data privacy. When asked about the existence of data privacy policies for digital library services, 62% of students said they were unaware of any such policies, and 52% of them believed the college had not communicated effectively about how students' data was being used or protected. Despite the low digital literacy levels, 75% of students expressed interest in attending more workshops and training sessions to improve their skills in using digital resources and learning about data privacy. They acknowledged that such programs would be beneficial in both their academic and personal digital practices.

8. Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations:

The findings of this study highlight critical gaps in digital literacy and data privacy awareness among undergraduate students at the college in West Bengal. Most students lacked the necessary skills to use digital library resources effectively and were unaware of basic cybersecurity practices. Although they were frequent users of digital platforms, especially social media, their negligence in protecting their personal information left them vulnerable to security threats. The majority of students struggle with using advanced digital tools, managing academic resources, and critically evaluating online content. A lack of concern and understanding regarding data privacy exposes students to potential risks of identity theft and data breaches. Students do not engage in basic online security measures, such as using strong passwords, VPNs, or regularly updating their software. Despite active use of social media, students are not taking the necessary precautions to protect their privacy online. The college is not providing sufficient resources, workshops, or information on digital literacy and data privacy, leaving students unprepared for digital security challenges.

Recommendations:

- Implement comprehensive digital literacy training programs to improve students' ability to use online resources effectively and responsibly.
- Raise awareness of data privacy risks through campaigns, workshops, and seminars that emphasize the importance of securing personal information in the digital age.
- Encourage best practices for online security by introducing mandatory training on password management, software updates, and safe internet browsing.
- Use social media for education by leveraging the platforms students frequently use to share tips and reminders about online security and privacy.
- Introduce clear data privacy policies for digital library resources, ensuring that students are informed about how their data is collected, used, and protected.
- These measures are critical for preparing students for the challenges of the digital world, ensuring both their academic success and their personal security.

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